

Digital-born Artifacts and Cultural Heritage

Approaching Swiss Video Game History through the Digital Humanities

- Adrian Demleitner, adrian.demleitner@hkb.bfh.ch
- Dr. Eugen Pfister, tobias.hodel@unibe.ch
- Dr. Tobias Hodel, eugen.pfister@hkb.bfh.ch
- Tao Fan, fantao@smail.nju.edu.cn

How can video game studies and digital humanities mutually enrich the study of digital-born cultural artifacts? This paper presents findings from Confoederatio Ludens, a research project exploring Swiss video game culture from 1968 until 2000 through interdisciplinary methodologies. By applying computational approaches such as distant viewing of visual corpora, critical source code analysis, and metadata modeling among others, we reveal previously overlooked aspects of Switzerland's video game history, such as local adaptations of global gaming trends and the distinctive technological practices of Swiss developers. Furthermore, our project demonstrates how concepts of locality and regional history contribute critically to digital humanities scholarship, challenging established narratives dominated by U.S.- and Japan-centric histories. Reflecting on our initial findings, we discuss both methodological challenges and opportunities emerging from the intersection of these two fields, emphasizing the importance of preservation, computational analysis, and local historical inquiry. Ultimately, our approach highlights the value of interdisciplinary methods for understanding digital artifacts not just as technological objects, but as culturally embedded historical sources.

Introduction

The 1980s witnessed the advent of the home computer, a period during which computing systems became commercially available and were marketed to private consumers (Haddon, 1988; Williams, 1976). Early models, including the ZX Spectrum, the Commodore 64, and the Atari ST, rapidly gained popularity in Europe, thereby facilitating the introduction of digital technology into households. This period also marked a first step towards the democratization of digital creation (Blankenheim, 2023; Navarro-Remesal & Pérez Latorre, 2022).

There is an increased need to study this history from a local point of view, which is was the research endeavour Confoederatio Ludens set out to do. As a larger project, the research perspectives and questions are diverse. They are unified by the simple inquiry into the relations between the arrival of digital technology and the birth of the video game industry in Switzerland in the 1980s and 1990s. This article will only be able to cover the Confoederatio Ludens research project partially. In the following, a specific focus is layed on the relation between the digital humanities and video game studies with regard to research local history.

It can be argued that the history of digital technology is longer than that of the field of video game studies, starting with the first attempts to encode information (Petzold, 2022) and the work of Charles Babbage and Ada Lovelace on the analytical engine (Füegi & Francis, 2015). The study of video games began to gain traction in the late 1990s, and was formally established in

2001 with the establishment of the first peer-reviewed academic journal dedicated to the subject (Aarseth, 2001). Espen Aarseth contended that computer games constitute a distinctive cultural phenomenon, amalgamating aesthetic and social components (Aarseth, 2001). While advocating for their integration within extant academic disciplines, he asserted that computer games merit independent consideration as a distinct field of enquiry, eschewing assimilation into domains such as cinema, literature, or “new media”. Concurrently, Claus Pias delved into the foundational nexus between computers as universal machines and the game worlds they engender (Pias, 2010). He contends that computers themselves can be regarded as a distinct “meta-game” characterized by their set of symbols, rules, and outcomes, thereby prompting inquiries into the manner in which computerization has transformed game worlds in comparison to non-computerized games. Finally, Samuel Pizelo’s research provides a conclusion that synthesizes the preceding discussions (Pizelo, 2024). Pizelo’s study explores the utilization of games as modelling technologies for the Analytical Engine, the symbolic computational device developed by Charles Babbage and Ada Lovelace. The study contends that the historical progression of computing technology is but a segment of a more extensive historical trajectory of games as modelling technologies.

Graeme Kirkpatrick conducted a thorough examination of video game culture in the UK (Kirkpatrick, 2015). Alexis Blanchet and Guillaume Montagnon focused on France (Blanchet, 2020), while Melanie Swalwell explored the roots of homebrew culture in Australia and New Zealand (Swalwell, 2021). Jaroslav Švelch demonstrated the development of an independent video game culture in the 1980s in Czechoslovakia (Švelch, 2018). This research on local video game histories reveals that these narratives are not the slightest less interesting than the predominantly US-Japanese trajectory but represent vibrant markets and cultures in their own right. So far, Switzerland has been terra incognita regarding the history of video game development. Hence, the need for a reappraisal. Confoederatio Ludens joins the endeavour to inquire local video game histories and strives to add insights into the early history of video game development in Switzerland.

The Confoederatio Ludens research team encompasses several research disciplines and perspectives. The researched topics include the analysis of the developer community, arcades and computer clubs, design- and development-practices, analysis of material conditions such as development tools, media-analysis of the video games with a focus on visuality, sound and interaction, analysis of reception through video game magazine reviews as well as player experience, and finally, the research of electronic and computing hardware, all with a view on games developed in Switzerland. Such a multi-perspective approach allows for in-depth encounters with economic, social, and cultural developments regarding digital technologies, while catering to the urgent need to research and preserve this volatile piece of history. Whereas all the research participants start from the same corpus, everyone is expanding on it by their own perspective and enriches it with their own source material. Despite coming from different research backgrounds and methodologies, we unite in our research intentions towards the same goal, from our respective perspectives.

Video Game Studies and Digital Humanities: Methodological Challenges and Technical Perspectives

With the advent of video game studies at the beginning of the 21st century, the two major perspectives saw video games as either a continuation of literature in electronic form or focused on the games' ludic elements, rules and mechanics (Murray, 2005). Neither perspective emerged on its own but was constituted by an influx of researchers coming from other disciplines - literature and media studies, anthropology and sociology, computer science, psychology, design research, and many more, depending on what the research focus is. Unfolding from the two major perspectives, video game studies amalgamated many research approaches and methodologies. This disciplinary diversity points towards the complexity of video games as study objects. Not only are the psychological or societal aspects to be considered on behalf of players and developers, video games are also embedded in a complex technological context, on which development and play depends. As a rather young discipline, video game studies have not developed their own methodologies and epistemologies yet, but are up to this date highly dependent on other disciplines.

Since video games are digital-born objects, video game studies and digital humanities have overlapping research interests. Video games exceed in scope what we can cognitively grasp, consequently a veritable disorder presents itself to the researcher. If we want to examine these media, we must encounter them in their specific *technicity* (Omena, 2021). Inquiring about video games according to this medium's techno-material conditions has implications for our methodological toolbox. Computational and digital research methodologies can support research approaches in the humanities that traditionally concentrate on qualitative methods, including hermeneutical approaches. Of course, digital research subjects can profit from digital research methodologies. The focus on technological aspects of the research subject or the application of computational methodologies can help unravel complexities since they target aspects unique to video games.

Parts of the diverse field of video game studies are interested in studying games for practical reasons, such as to advance development and design practices. Others have research approaches with a critical background, often embedded in various humanities disciplines. Similarly, digital humanities research often incorporates inquiries on information technologies with critical humanities approaches. They often apply critical perspectives and methodologies such as source criticism, contextualization of research study and approach, critical inquiry on technology, or uncovering technology's entanglement with power dynamics in gender and race.

Computational approaches to researching video games are in their infancy at the time of writing. Video games are amalgamates of different media such as graphics, video and animation, text and sound as well as peripheral technologies such as controllers and screens. As such, they bring a plethora of material to be analysed through distant viewing. The computational analysis of sound and video, similar to the analysis of film, already shows promising results (Burghardt & Piontkowitz, 2024). These approaches are costly in terms of computing resources and can only capture video games partially due to that limitation. To analyse several hours of gameplay video, computing resource limitations require that only screenshots of these videos can be processed.

This is a regression from interactive gameplay, to a recorded video and then to a corpus of screenshots. What is lost in this process is the aspect of interactivity, as well as the medium's relation to time and animation.

This reduction in scope is inherent to distant reading approaches, but not unique to them. To analyse larger amounts of data, it must be processed and brought into a form that allows comparison, or that certain aspects are left out. Distant viewing or machine learning often needs images to be the same resolution, and they have to be pre-processed and often reduced in size. Similarly, text-corpus analysis usually ignores the layout of the text, which can have hermeneutic importance. All analytical methodologies suffer from such a fate, and so do distant viewing approaches in video game studies. This highlights the important to reflect on the applied method and what is lost in the process.

The last aspect is related to digital humanities inherent closeness to practical engagements with technology and partially based on my own observation. In digital humanities as well as video game studies, researchers can't avoid intimate exploration and encounters of technology. In both domains, technologies need to be practised and can't be accessed by observation alone. This relates again to the *technicity* of the medium (Omena, 2021), the relation we have with technology. Computing systems and their software must be met in their own material conditions. Be it in setting up scripting or emulation environments, dealing with the quirks and specificities of different computing systems, or the general frustration of failing software. Researchers who proliferate in these fields are often willing and capable of dealing with these issues. Difficult access limits who can research technological research topics by enacting time and resource constraints. This, in turn, limits who is able to produce profound critique in these areas. This also limits who can produce knowledge that, in the end, shapes our relation to technology. This limited access to researching such technologies and, hence, their power dynamics needs to be an important point of reflection and critique in either field. ### A Framework for Convergence

The intersection of video game studies and digital humanities creates a framework organized around three key areas: **preservation**, **research methodologies**, and **theoretical approaches**. In preservation, video games as born-digital objects present unique challenges that digital humanities addresses through **metadata standardization** initiatives like the Video Game Ontology (VGO) and Linked Open Data (LOD), **emulation and virtualization techniques** developed by organizations such as the Internet Archive and the Video Game History Foundation, and the **study of source code archives** as developed by Marino (Marino, 2020). These approaches treat games as cultural heritage worthy of systematic documentation and long-term accessibility.

Within this framework, research methodologies are categorized into computational approaches (e.g., distant viewing, corpus-based analysis) and critical humanities approaches (e.g., close reading, critical code analysis, ethnographic and sourcecritical methods). Distant reading techniques include distant viewing of game visuals inspired by Burghardt's work on computational game studies (Burghardt & Piontkowitz, 2024) or corpus-based analysis of development trends akin to Moretti's distant reading approach (Moretti, 2013). These computational methods enable large-scale analysis of game design trends and historical trajectories.

Close reading methodologies complement distant approaches by employing critical code studies, ethnographic analyses of player interactions (following Taylor’s conceptualization) (Taylor, 2009), and design-based research. Additionally, they incorporate paratextual analysis—based on Genette’s framework (Genette, 1997)—to examine game manuals, marketing materials, and associated communities. Together, these varied methodologies provide comprehensive analytical tools for understanding games as both computational systems and cultural artifacts requiring multiple perspectives.

The theoretical dimension of this framework emphasizes the importance of local contexts in digital game cultures, challenging established narratives dominated by U.S. and Japanese perspectives and highlighting diverse cultural and technological conditions shaping local video game histories. This approach examines how video games are shaped by local technological infrastructures, economic conditions, and cultural preferences through concepts like “vernacular digitality” (Swalwell, 2021) and regional game histories (Švelch, 2018). The framework acknowledges the importance of local knowledge production in computational research (Fiormonte, 2016) and incorporates place-based methodologies including digital mapping and regional archival work. This structured understanding creates a dynamic, evolving model that strengthens the coherence between theoretical discussions and empirical research while accommodating emerging methodologies in both fields.

Confoederatio Ludens Research Corpora: Metadata, Visual Analysis, and Source Code

The research team at Confoederatio Ludens is characterized by considerable interdisciplinarity, encompassing the fields of history of technology, video game design, sociology, video game studies, gender studies, and the digital humanities. In the subsequent discussion, the focus will be directed exclusively towards aspects pertaining to the digital humanities, with particular emphasis on three research areas and interests deemed pertinent to the present research project: the humanities of the digital, digitized humanities, and the computational humanities (Burghardt & Piontkowitz, 2024). These three overarching domains within the digital humanities are further delineated into specific research objectives within the scope of the Confoederatio Ludens project, namely the exploration of video game history through the utilization of metadata, the investigation of video games as digital artefacts, and the examination of distant reading and viewing methodologies. The aforementioned elements are addressed through the engagement with three distinct yet interconnected digital corpora, which are intricately linked to the research priorities of the Confoederatio Ludens.

1. A comprehensive list of Swiss video games from the 1980ies and 1990ies and their accompanying metadata, such as factual information, computing systems, genre, and actors involved in the development and distribution
2. A catalogue of images and visual material from the video games, such as screenshots or scans of paratextual material
3. An archive containing original, uncrunched¹ or decompiled source code of relevant

1 Uncrunching is a technique that makes optimized source code readable again. Crunching compacts and reorganizes source code in order to save space.

games

In this methodological approach, inspiration is drawn from other research projects and preservation approaches, with which the common goal of investigating local video game histories is shared. We'd like to highlight the work done by the *Residual Media Depot*² at the Concordia University in Montréal and the *Learning Games Initiative*³ at the University of Arizona. Both collect video games, consoles, and related material for active research. The much larger *Video Games History Foundation*⁴, also based in the United States, is dedicated to preserving and teaching the history of video games. Meanwhile, the national libraries of France⁵ and Germany⁶ have ongoing efforts to create national registers and archives of their respective countries' video game history.

Metadata

Metadata, data about data, is an essential first framing of the research object and a way of getting an overview. Since we are mainly interested in the context of the video games' coming into being, a lot of our metadata concentrates on the actors that developed and published a game. Most of the video game metadata and ontology projects, such as Video Game Ontology (VGO), Digital Game Ontology (DGO), and Game Metadata and Citation Project (GAMECIP), concentrate on describing the contents of a game and are also partially abandoned (Martino et al., 2023). Since we're more interested in a historic contextualisation of video games and their development practices, we will not be able to build on top of these metadata ontology projects. Instead, we started working with Wikidata to give the data structure and adhere to linked open data and FAIR/CARE (Beretta, 2021; Carroll et al., 2020) principles.

Until today, there were only a handful of reliable sources regarding video games developed in Switzerland, and most of them contained partial and unstructured information. Initially, we estimated a rough 50 video games that we could add to our research corpus. We based this number on the entries in the Swiss Games Garden⁷ database, a project that collects video games that relate to Switzerland. The database's entries showed games being developed and published throughout the 1980ies and 1990ies, with a dip after the dot-com bubble crash⁸ in the late 90ies. With the help of a joint-venture research inquiry of early video games in the German-speaking countries by Eugen Pfister (Pfister, 2023), we were able to triple our initial estimate. We approach acquiring metadata and discovering unaccounted video games through different means. An important source were video game databases created and maintained by amateurs, digitized magazine and newspaper archives, archived webpages, and personal contact with the video game developers of the past (Pfister et al., 2023).

Our corpus of roughly 150 video games contains entries that were developed in Switzerland, but

2 [residual media depot](#), accessed 2025-01-03

3 [Learning Games Initiative Research Archive \(LGIRA\)](#), accessed 2025-01-03

4 [Video Game History Foundation](#), accessed 2025-01-03

5 [Les jeux vidéo à la BnF](#), accessed 2025-01-03

6 [Computerspiele - DLA Marbach](#), accessed 2025-01-03

7 [Swiss Games Garden](#), accessed 2024-03-15 11:56

8 [Dot-com bubble - Wikipedia](#), accesses 2024-02-06 11:34

not necessarily published here, and are mostly games that were commercially listed. Inquiring amateur- or indie-games might be beyond the scope of our project, since the approach to collecting this data needs to be more participatory and aiming at longer time-frames. The metadata corpus is at the heart of Confoederatio Ludens. Since we're breaking into new grounds here, we want and need to have a comprehensive and detailed overview. All our different disciplinary and methodological approaches depend on knowing what is out there regarding Swiss video games. From following leads to distant reading patterns in video game development, the metadata corpus is the starting point for all inquiries.

Images

Next to qualitative approaches through design research and video game development studies, we aim at a distant reading approach of an image corpus containing screenshots of all relevant games. The inquiry questions comparatively the state of the art of video game graphic design in other countries, the evolution of video game design in Switzerland over time, the relationship between video game graphics and the technological means, but also if there are unique stylistic specifics regarding video game design in Switzerland or parts of the country. The screenshots are collected from various databases, for example MobyGames⁹, which offers an API for the retrieval of images. The methodological approach is based on the computational method of distant viewing to analyze visual patterns across a large dataset of video game screenshots, allowing for examination of historical development beyond individual case studies (Demleitner, 2024a). The analysis revealed both the potential of this approach for studying video game history at scale and its challenges, including visualization difficulties due to video games' visual diversity, while also highlighting the deep connections between video game design, computing history, and popular culture. Although well-structured, databases like MobyGames often only offer a limited perspective on a video game's graphics (Pfister et al., 2023).

The production of screenshots from a video game is at the same time methodologically limiting. It is a regress from a game, a so-called ergodic media (Aarseth, 1997), to mere static images. The gameness or dimension of gameplay is lost in this process, and only traces of it are present in the final product. Sebastian Möring calls the screenshot's dependency on the source game conditional cyberimage (Gerling et al., 2023). The loss of this aspect in the screenshots needs to be considered when analysing the visual material. Screencasts would only partially solve the problem of the loss of ergodicity while introducing other problems. We exclude videos from the analysis as of now since they introduce new technical considerations and research problematics, such as the analysis of progression in time, the storage of the collected media, or how to code videos properly. This aspect will remain problematic for now, as some semantic meaning only reveals itself in animations, such as special effects that indicate a change in the game state.

Next to formal and semiotic elements and paratextual material, the Framework for the Analysis of Visual Representation in Video Games (FAVR) (Arsenault et al., 2015) of categorization for the visuality of a digital game is applied to collect material. FAVR is clear in outline and scope and is mainly considering the macro and material perspective on the image in digital games. Formal and semiotic elements can vary in scope and their analysis focuses on the micro level of

9 [Video Game Database - MobyGames](#), accessed 2024-03-18 13:06

a game. Decisions must be made with each game, slightly adjusting what is collected. This approach follows loosely along compositional analysis, whereas the FAVR takes over the spatial components and semiotic analysis over content. To work pragmatically, we are in the process of building a proper ontology on top of this conceptual model (Demleitner, 2024b) that can then be applied in image research software such as *Tropy*¹⁰.

Source Code

In parallel, we are also building a corpus with the source code of the games in question. The 1980ies marked the arrival of the home-computer. It was a time when computing systems became affordable and got marketed to private consumers. Early 8-bit systems, such as the Atari, the Commodore 64 or the Apple II, quickly became popular in Europe and opened the door for digitality to enter the home [Haddon (1988); williamsEarlyComputersEurope1976]. This period also marks a first step towards the democratization of digital creation (Blankenheim, 2023; Navarro-Remesal & Pérez Latorre, 2022). The computing systems were often equipped with software for text editing or creating digital graphics and music. All these systems came as well with various features to write code and software programs. Whereas the former were adaptations of traditional forms to creative expression into the digital realm, the latter represented a novel approach for such endeavours.

Video games combine these affordances uniquely while translating human intention into instructions that a computing system understands - into computer code. Programming, in return, offers novel ways of creation. To this day, acquiring programming knowledge and skills is no easy feat. It takes practice, is time-consuming, and can be highly frustrating. The question is, *why would someone want to do that, voluntarily?* Especially to create an interactive work that wasn't necessarily financially or socially rewarding.

The source code of the researched games is of special interest to us in particular. Source code is text containing instructions for the computer. It is structured according to the rules of programming languages. We can divide these into high- and low-level languages. With the growing complexity of microchips and the manner of instructing them to do their work, punch cards and writing machinecode couldn't keep up. Low-level languages like assembly offer little abstraction, but already provide basic routines a programmer would need to do regularly. An example would be to move data from one place in the memory to another to process it. Low-level languages are still intimately tied to the hardware they would run on. A programmer would not only need to know the specifics of the language but also those of the hardware and microchips. High-level programming languages, in turn, offer strong abstraction from such details.

Once written as plain text source code, it then has to be translated into machine code. Source code is still a human product, made for the human mind as a working tool. Computing systems will not know what to do from such a textual artefact. The translation into machine code can be done through compiling or interpretation. Both approaches use additional software tools to prepare the source code for the machine. This means that we usually have at least two different

¹⁰ [Explore your research photos | Tropy](#), accessed 2024-03-19 10:52

states of a game. The developers' intentions captured in the source code, which is not executable, and the machine's understanding of these intentions, playable. The codebase of the second product of this process can't be read by humans. It is important to point out, that this is a one-way process. Once being transformed into an executable video game, we can't extract the original source code from it. The process of translation into machine code strips away many elements that are important for human reading and meaning-making, but not for machine understanding.

Critical code analysis treats code not only as functional instructions to a machine, but also as a text that can be hermeneutically approached and semiotically read (Marino, 2020). This approach applies critical hermeneutics to interpreting computer code, program architecture, and documentation within a socio-historical context. Further, from the perspective of design theory, a digital game is a second order design (Willumsen, 2016). Game developers only indirectly produce the game. Instead, they design the structures that generate the game. Akin to the writing aid for an author, like pens or keyboards, source code has a formal and structural influence on what and how the game developers design. Taken together, these two approaches outline source code as a carrier of meaning and the tools and material for designing games. This makes source code a core focus.

Working with source code can be difficult. It is text but can reach levels of abstraction down to being a string of seemingly random alphanumeric strings. This is, for example, the case with assembly, the programming language used to instruct microchips to do computing tasks directly. A certain level of knowledge and experience is needed to dive into source code with close readings fruitfully. Initial attempts with critical code analysis, the close reading of source code, led to meaningful insights, but the code's structure withdraws established approaches for now (Demleitner, 2023a). We've been left with the question, how can the digital humanities treat source code, respecting its specific textuality? Distant reading approaches, in which the digital humanities are especially strong, are yet to be established when approaching source code.

Often, we need to contact the original developers and ask if they kept their games' source code. In other cases, source code is easily accessible. Basic, an early high-level language, is not always compiled into machine code and was very popular with video game developers in the 1980ies. With some knowledge of Commodore 64 Basic, one is able to stop a running game and dive into it's source code. Before the advent of floppy disks, magazine listings were a way of distributing games. Instead of physical data storage, the video game code was printed in a magazine. The reader then had to copy the listing and type the code on their machine to be able to play the game. Game listings only make up a small portion of our corpus.

Further Methodological Considerations

All three corpora will touch on distant reading or viewing approaches, where the digital humanities excel. Especially regarding digital corpora, distant readings will aid in getting an overview and seeing what is present and missing. Distant reading methods are a humanist approach to dealing with large amounts of data and attempts to find patterns in such large corpora. The patterns are not necessarily imminent and pre-present in the data, but correspond

with the researcher's questions to the corpus. Once the researcher can see uniformities, they can also see where there are gaps and sub-sequentially ask why these gaps exist. It is not only interesting to understand why and how patterns relate to the research questions, but also to figure out if certain areas might have been under-researched.

In a best-case scenario, we will also be able to identify patterns in our data or find connections we didn't see before. How we can approach our source code archive in such a manner is yet to be seen, and an interesting research gap. Source code is clearly text, but to what extent can it be treated through textual analysis, common to the digital humanities? In a recent case study (Demleitner, 2023a) one of the biggest problems was the non-linearity of source code. There is no clear beginning and no clear end. Instead, it is highly networked and self-referential. Parts are included and reused, modularized and broken up into pieces.

Corpus analysis was developed with the study of human language in mind (Huang & Yao, 2015). Literary text produced by humans and for human consumption is of another structural logic than source code, which is intended for machines. Source code is structured closer to something like logic. The inscription and extraction of meaning from these texts then acquire different ways of reading. There are unique structures, for example the branching and jumping into different places of the text through the *if this, then that* logic. Branches can lead to loops so that we would encounter the same places in source code over and over again. This has led to critical code analysis staying close to qualitative methodologies and close readings of source code (Marino, 2020).

Preservation is a further topic that needs to be considered. These video games, that we are investigating, are a mere 30 to 40 years old. It became apparent, how much time that is in terms of software and software development. None of the computing systems of the 1980ies and 90ies are in use or at in active maintenance any more. All these systems, from the *ZX Spectrum*, and *Commodore 64*, to older DOS systems and the Classic MacIntosh are only kept alive by a small but active amateur and research community. Also, many of the developers who worked on the games we're interested in are in their 70ies. This means, we are very close to losing direct access to knowledge about this game.

It is tantamount to video game research to play these games. Most of the games we investigate can be emulated. But since we're not only interested in the game itself, but also its development, we need to have access to original systems, their development environments as well as the developers themselves. Even if the topic of preservation is not of direct interest to us, we are engaging in it (Demleitner, 2023b). Next to acquiring the original hardware and computing systems that are needed to run the games, we are also testing and playing the games in simulated environments. Emulators are software, that reproduce the hardware specifics of older computing systems virtually. Although the playing experience can differ, this type of software is invaluable for our research. Many of the games that we're interested in, are only available as virtual copies, so-called disk dumps, and can be found online. Our team at the ZHdK is specialised on collecting the originally published video games as well as their paratextual material, such as packaging or manuals (Suter, 2023a).

Early Swiss Video Game Development: Initial Findings

It can be argued that video games are strongly related to local and global aspects of cultural and national identities. Melanie Swallow developed the term ‘vernacular digitality’ (Swallow, 2021) to emphasise how early digital technologies were appropriated and used in everyday, localized contexts, thus highlighting how different cultures and communities engaged with and shaped digital technologies. Jaroslav Švelch, on the other hand, challenged Western-centric narratives: By examining the history of gaming in a Soviet bloc country (Švelch, 2018), he outlined how Czechoslovakian gamers and developers adapted global gaming trends to their local context, creating informal economies and using gaming for political expression. Furthermore, Souvik Mukherjee takes a postcolonial perspective in his work on video game history in the Indian subcontinent (*Videogames in the Indian Subcontinent*, n.d.). Building on his earlier work, Mukherjee addresses issues of equality and diversity within video game studies.

One year into the project, the first findings and patterns regarding local and global dimensions are emerging. In the following section, we provide some insights from our research project, Confoederatio Ludens. In this first year, we worked on getting a general overview. We needed to know how many video games were developed in Switzerland until the year 2000, who worked on those, but also where the games were played, in terms of geographical area, and computing systems.

As outlined before, we are in the process of modelling this corpus’ metadata and adding it to Wikidata. The Wikidata Video Game Project proposes a few basic attributes¹¹ that help to describe a video game, as well as contextualizing it. Their model is similar in scope and detail to specialized databases, such as *MobyGames* or *Hall of Light*¹², with the added benefit that Wikidata adheres to FAIR/CARE and is a form of linked open data. Working with Wikidata, a larger issue becomes evident. Although acquisition and structuring of basic data on a video game is fairly straightforward, it is not sufficient to approach a core question of Confoederatio Ludens: What is a Swiss video game? It becomes apparent, from the perspective of metadata, that attribution of nationality can’t be easily achieved.

It is a key takeaway, that reflecting on Swissness is a mandatory task, that we must engage with again and again. What makes a video game a Swiss video game? The question is trivial, but crediting nationality to a game can be complex. In our research project, video games are windows into complicated pasts where cultural, social, economic, and political movements and changes entangle. Most of the crediting of nationality is based on the actors who produced the game. If the developing studio or most people working on the game were registered in Switzerland, it’s considered a Swiss game. But that definition sometimes becomes useless to our research focus.

Already in the 1980ies, video games were sometimes developed by international teams or published by companies outside of Switzerland. In such cases, it helps to rephrase our research

11 Details about the proposed and institutionalised model can be found on [WikiProject Video Games Properties](#), accessed 2024-03-15 14:06

12 [Hall Of Light - The database of Amiga games](#), accessed 2024-03-19

interest. We're interested in the advent of digitality in Switzerland, seen through the lenses of video game studies. An interesting case, for example, is posed by Samo Jordan. He ported *Wipeout2097* (Psygnosis/Psygnosis, 1996, PlayStation) from the PlayStation to the Amiga/PowerPC in 1999. *Wipeout2097* is certainly not a Swiss game per definition, but it's interesting to our inquiry since the port of that game is intertwined with the acquisition of video game development knowledge by a Swiss person.

The proposed model by the Wikidata Video Game Project¹³ can reach its limits in these cases, especially regarding our research interest. The model proposes *country of origin* to ascribe nationality, and although multiple values are possible, not much reasoning beyond a reference can be added to such a statement. With smaller productions, amateur- or indie-games, country of origin can easily be ascribed, when the staff has Swiss citizenship and worked on the game in Switzerland. In others, the concept of *Helvetica*¹⁴ is a better approach. The Swiss National Library defines something as Helvetica if the following conditions are met.

- a. published in Switzerland;
- b. relates to Switzerland or to people with Swiss citizenship or domicile; or
- c. created or co-created by Swiss authors or authors associated with Switzerland.

To that end, we had to thoroughly research and collect metadata on the actors who worked on the video games. Gathering knowledge on the people behind the game is often more complex, since we're usually left with nothing more than a name as well as the role of the person in a video games' development. Those names come from various sources closely related to the games themselves - screenshots of video game intros or ending titles, scans of manuals or packaging, interviews and post-mortems in magazines, and archived webpages. Some of the larger video game databases, such as MobyGames or Hall of Light, often contain that kind of knowledge as well, which helps in triangulating the validity of the information. Although, when using these amateur-platforms as a source, we have to be wary of the reliability of their knowledge. The information presented has seldomly been verified in a manner that allows a researcher to back-trace the source of knowledge (Pfister et al., 2023).

A first attempt at thoroughly capturing those developer teams and modelling them into Wikidata unwrapped a first glimpse into the commercial video game development scene in the 1980ies to 90ies in Switzerland. In the German-speaking part of Switzerland, we have one big hub of activity that centred around Linel (Suter, 2023b), a development studio and publisher. Linel wasn't a fixed entity, but a loose network of game developers from Switzerland and the UK, that worked for Linel on a project-to-project basis. Besides that, we have a few smaller studios, that only developed one or two games, but often continued producing software and following a career in IT or studying informatics. Lastly, we have a few developers or developer teams, that made amateur games, some of which even were sold.¹⁵

Switzerland was certainly not an important market for video games, and developing them not necessarily a sustainable career choice in the 1980ies and -90ies. The case of Linel showed, that

13 [Wikidata:WikiProject Video games/Properties - Wikidata](#), accessed 2024-01-30 11:20

14 [Helvetica \(Bibliothekswesen\) - Wikipedia](#)

15 Relevant SPARQL queries can be found on the Wikidata profile [User:Thgiex - Wikidata](#), accessed 2024-03-15 14:12

only companies with strong international ties and relations management could sustain themselves over longer time. This is somewhat in contrast to the video game development scene in the neighbouring and German-speaking country, Austria. Several game development studios proved, through their own trajectories, that video game development can be a viable and successful business (Pfister, 2021). Besides these categories, a lot of video game development was happening around Swiss universities, which became especially evident in the French-speaking part of Switzerland. In the 1970ies and 80ies, Jean-Daniel Nicoud developed the Smaky computer at the EPFL and used video game development as a prime pedagogic method to teach programming skills (Nicoud, 1991). For some of the people we found, working on video games was a good way to earn some extra money during the university studies.

Next to the who, it is also important to look at the what. It is an important observation, that many of the commercially listed games were adaptations of established game concepts. At Linel, for example, we find game concepts that were successful in the 1980ies, re-adapted with new stories, graphics and features. This points towards certain economic needs, where copying an established video game is the lesser financial risk than investing plenty of resources in entirely new developments, while at the same time offering valuable time to learn digital skills and acquire knowledge. The games produced by amateurs, on the other hand, often leaned towards role playing games or similarly narrative genres. In both categories, global pop-cultural influences become clearly visible, often through references to other games, popular sci-fi and fantasy films and series, comics, or songs of the time.

Another aspect that we are looking into is the production process. What tools and technologies were used to produce these games? Here we come very close again to digital humanities focus on technology as a study object, but also to design research which is interested in design practices. A good example is what programming languages were used to develop the games.

So far we have only 31 games where assumptions on used programming languages could be made with a high certainty, usually through statements by the developers. Philipp Gressly Freimann, for example, listed three programming languages for both of the two games he worked on, on his website¹⁶. For many of the games in our corpus, the programming language needs to be assumed. Most of the pre-DOS games for Smaky probably were written in *CALM*, since they were programmed by Jean-Daniel Nicoud, who invented the Smaky as well as *CALM* (Wagner & Nicoud, 1987). For some of the games produced by Linel, *68000 assembly*¹⁷ could be a probable candidate, especially if Christian Haller or Christian Weber worked on it¹⁸. These two regularly worked on video games for Linel and stated to program in *68000 assembly*. Some games that were published for different computing systems could share code across platforms, after which adjustments were made to take advantage of the specific hardware. While sharing the Motorola 68000 microprocessor with the Atari ST, the Amiga for example had easier routines to work with video game graphics.

The gathering of the *programmed in*¹⁹ attribute gave us a good idea of the development space and

16 [Philipps Seiten](#), accessed 2024-03-19

17 [Motorola 68000 - Wikipedia](#), accessed 2024-03-18 13:49

18 [Amiga Games](#) and [Christian A. Weber's Commodore Amiga projects](#), accessed 2024-03-19

19 [programmed in - Wikidata](#), accessed 2024-03-18 13:51

some of its specifics. Amateur games were most likely approached in a BASIC dialect, while the commercial games were written by people that were knowledgeable in assembly. An interesting position here takes *CALM*, which is not an assembly dialect, but an assembly notation system. It was an attempt to write the same code, but for multiple different microprocessor architectures. This would enable portability between different computing architectures and is still a topic as of today (*The Unnecessary Obscurity of Assembly Language*, 2023; wd5gnr, 2015/2024).

Conclusion: Integrating Video Game Studies and Digital Humanities

The intersection of video game studies and digital humanities presents a rich, yet methodologically complex landscape. Our exploration of this convergence through the Confoederatio Ludens project reveals that both fields share key concerns in the preservation, analysis, and interpretation of digital-born media. While we are still in the early phases of building our research corpus as a common denominator across different disciplines, our intermittent findings indicate promising results. Digital humanities approaches offer robust methodological foundations through metadata modeling, distant viewing, and critical code analysis, while video game studies contribute new perspectives on digital objects that are multimodal, interactive, and dependent on technological infrastructures. This reciprocal relationship demonstrates how computational methods can extend analytical scope beyond traditional close readings of game content and player reception.

Our experience highlights both challenges and opportunities in this interdisciplinary space. Digital humanities approaches often require large corpora to leverage distant reading or viewing methodologies effectively, which presents limitations at this early stage of our project. However, we anticipate overcoming this issue once we begin analyzing our image and source code corpora, which exceed some qualitative approaches either through size or complexity. Meanwhile, metadata modeling has proven invaluable for critically reflecting on our corpus scope. As writing can be an extension of thinking, describing video games through metadata helps sharpen research focus while highlighting fundamental questions about how to define what constitutes a video game—an ongoing discourse in the field.

A significant contribution of our work has been the incorporation of **locality** into digital humanities approaches to video game research. The Confoederatio Ludens project emphasizes the importance of regional game histories, recognizing that video game cultures are shaped by specific technological, social, and economic contexts. This approach aligns with recent efforts in digital humanities to move beyond dominant Anglophone narratives and account for the diverse, localized conditions under which digital artifacts are produced and experienced. By positioning Swiss video game history within a structured digital humanities framework, we illustrate how computational tools can help uncover overlooked histories, reinforcing the critical role of place-based methodologies in both fields.

Looking forward, this research contributes to an evolving framework for the study of video games in digital humanities—one that is both structured and adaptable. It is safe to say that video game studies is a fascinating field for digital humanities due to the digital nature of games as

research objects, their multimodal complexity, and the need for interdisciplinary approaches. Video games often exceed the scope of purely qualitative approaches through the mass of possible media to be analyzed, the entangled network of actors developing games, and their dependency on technological infrastructures. Future work must continue refining the integration of **computational, archival, and critical methodologies**, ensuring a reciprocal dialogue between fields. The challenges of analyzing video game source code call for interdisciplinary approaches combining digital humanities expertise with game design and software studies, while methodological gaps in distant reading and visual analysis highlight the need for further experimentation with AI-driven pattern recognition and semantic modeling. By building on these foundations, researchers can continue to refine the theoretical and methodological bridges between these two fields, ensuring that video games are not only preserved as cultural artifacts but critically examined as dynamic, evolving objects of study in the digital age.

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